

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF WATER
SOLUBLE VITAMINS BY RP-HPLC METHOD**

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ABSTRACT

A simple, accurate and precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of Water-soluble vitamins are Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and thiamine nitrate in capsules dosage form on Agilent C18 column (150mmx4.6mm dia., 5 μ particle size), using buffer and acetonitrile in the ratio of 85:15 V/V, which was pumped through the column with a flow rate of 1mL/min. The buffer used in this method was 0.1% orthophosphoric acid at a pH of 2.5. The run time was 15 min. Detection was carried out at 280 nm. The retention times of retention time of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate were found to be 2.78min, 4.54min, 5.66 min, 6.31 min, 8.3min and 14.09min respectively. The regression analysis data indicated a good linear relationship for the calibration plots for Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate in the range of 375 to 1125 μ g/ml, 250-750 μ g/ml, 5 to 15 μ g/ml, 15 to 45 μ g/ml, 50 to 150 μ g/ml and 50 to 150 μ g/ml respectively. The regression coefficient was 0.9994, 0.9998, 0.9999, 0.9996, 0.9998 and 0.9968, respectively. The accuracy and reliability of the developed method were established by means of comparing numerous validation parameters like linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, specificity, the limit of quantification and limit of detection, in keeping with the ICH guidelines. The proposed method can be used for the estimation of these multicomponents of vitamins and other formulations.

Keywords: Water soluble vitamins, multicomponent formulation, Rp-HPLC, simultaneous estimation, marketed formulation

INTRODUCTION

The water-soluble vitamin supplements are Ascorbic acid -Vitamin C (**Fig .1**) is chemically (5R)-[(1S)-1,2-Dihydroxyethyl]-3,4-dihydroxyfuran-2(5H)-one use to prevent and treat scurvy. Niacin (B3) Nicotinamide (**Fig.2**) is chemically pyridine-3-carboxamide, used to treat skin disorders, anxiety, Alzheimer's disease. Pyridoxine (B6) (**Fig.3**) Pyridoxine HCl Chemically, 4, 5-Bis (hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpyridin-3-ol hydrochloride, used to treat nausea and vomiting in early pregnancy. Folic Acid(**Fig.4**) is chemically (2S)-2-[(4-[(2-amino-4-hydroxypteridin-6-yl)methyl]amino}phenyl)formamido]pentanedioic acid used as help the body convert food (carbohydrates) into fuel (glucose), which is used to produce energy. Riboflavin is (**Fig.5**) chemically is chemically 7,8-Dimethyl-10-[(2S,3S,4R)-2,3,4,5-tetrahydroxypentyl]benzo[g]pteridine-2,4-dione is used to micro nutrient with a key role in maintaining human health and thiamine nitrate is (**Fig.6**) chemically, 2-[3-[(4-amino-2-methylpyrimidin-5-yl) methyl]-4-methyl-1, 3-thiazol-3-ium-5-yl] ethanol hydrochloride, used to treat ulcerative colitis. The literature survey revealed that a few analytical methods have been reported for the estimation of these vitamins individually or in combination with other vitamins by, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography reversed-phase ion-pair high performance liquid chromatography⁷⁻²³. In this present work, an attempt was made to develop a simple, feasible and simultaneous determination of vitamins B1, B6, B12, B2, B3 and Vitamin C in combined multivitamin capsule by RP-HPLC. The proposed method was validated in accordance with International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines

Vitamin C (Fig I)

Nicotinamide (B3) (Fig.II)

Pyridoxine (B6) (Fig.III)

Folic Acid (Fig IV)

Riboflavin (B2) (Fig V)

Thiamine (B1) (Fig.VI)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemical and Reagents

Pure samples of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and thiamine nitrate gift sample by Sri Krishna Pharmaceuticals Ltd and the Madras Pharmaceuticals, Chennai. The capsule formulation is obtained from FOURTS-B (Label claim Ascorbic acid 75mg, Nicotinamide 50mg, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride 2mg, Folic Acid 1mg, Riboflavin 10mg and thiamine nitrate 10mg) was procured from the local market. HPLC grade acetonitrile and methanol were purchased from Merck India Limited (Mumbai, India). Water HPLC grade was obtained from a Milli-Q water purification system used throughout the analysis. Analytical reagent grade glacial acetic acid was purchased from Avantor (Maharashtra, India),

Experimental

To develop a suitable LC method for the analysis of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and thiamine nitrate in their combined dosage form, different mobile phases were tried. The criteria employed for selecting the mobile phase for the analysis of the drugs were cost involved, time required for the analysis and better separation of drugs⁷⁻²³. The chromatographic system consisted of pump (Shimadzu LC 10AT VP) with universal loop injector (Rheodyne 7725 i) of injection capacity 20 μ L. Detector consists of photodiode array detector (PDA) SPD-10 AVP UV-Visible detector and column used was Chromatopak C18 (25cm \times 4.6mm i.d. \times 5 μ m). The equipment was controlled by a PC work station equipped with software CLASS M 10-VP software (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan).

Preparation of standard stock solutions

The equivalents of 100 mg of Thiamine nitrate and 100 mg of Riboflavin, 30 mg of Pyridoxine hydrochloride and 10 mg of Folic acid were transferred into clean and dry 100 ml standard flask add 20ml glacial acetic acid sonicate, dissolve and make with diluent. Filter the solution through 0.45 μ PVDF syringe filter ratio (V/V) to prepare standard stock solutions. 75 mg of Ascorbic acid and 50mg of Nicotinamide transferred into clean and dry 100 ml standard flask. And add 10 ml of diluents sonicate to dissolve and make up the volume with diluents. Prepare standard stock solutions, after the immediate dissolution; the volume was made up to the mark with diluents. These standard stock solutions were observed to contain 100 μ g/ml of Thiamine nitrate and Riboflavin, 30 μ g/ml of Pyridoxine hydrochloride, 10 μ g/ml of Folic acid, 750 μ g/ml of Ascorbic acid and 500 μ g/ml of Nicotinamide).

For the preparation of the stock solution of tablet dosage form, 20 capsules of Fourts B were taken and their average weight was determined. They were powder equivalent to 525mg then in 20mL of glacial acetic acid and 10mL of diluent and heat in water bath for 20 minutes with vigorous shaking for 5-10 minutes. The liquid was cool and make to 100mL with diluents. Filter the solution through 0.45 μ PVDF syringe filter ratio (V/V) to prepare sample solutions.

A series of aqueous mobile phases containing sodium salt of 1-hexane sulphonic acid and glacial acetic acid buffer solutions of different pH values in combination with different volume fractions of acetonitrile as modifiers were also tried. The best result was obtained at pH 7.5 for sodium salt of 1-hexane sulphonic acid and glacial acetic acid buffer (pH adjusted with ammonium acetate). Further, the method was optimized by changing the concentration of the mobile phase. From the study, it was found that best result was obtained in quality separation in terms of peak symmetry, resolution, reasonable run time and other parameters by use of 85:15 (V/V) ratio mixture buffer and acetonitrile pH 7.5 (adjusted with ammonium acetate) as mobile phase. The flow rate was determined testing effect different flow rates of peak and resolution, flow rate 1mL/min found optimum.

VALIDATION

Selectivity of the method towards the drugs was established through study of resolution factor between the drug peaks. Under the proposed chromatographic conditions, all the six drugs were completely separated from each other with a resolution the retention time of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and thiamine nitrate was found to be 2.7min, 4.5min, 5.6min, 6.3min, 8.3min and 14.0min respectively. It indicates that the method is selective for simultaneous chromatograms of tablet solution with

the placebo solution and also with the chromatograms obtained from standard drugs. As the retention times for all the six drugs were same in standard solution as well as in tablet solution and also there was no extra peak co-eluted for diluents estimation of all the six drugs in commercial formulation.

For analysis of sample, six replicates of sample solutions were prepared and 20 μ L of each replicate was injected into the system and their chromatograms were recorded (Fig. 1). From the chromatograms it was observed that Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and thiamine nitrate were eluted at 2.7 min, 4.5 min, 5.6 min, 6.3 min, 8.3 min and 14.0 min with a resolution of each peaks was found more than 2 min. The total run time was 15 min. The concentrations of all the six drugs were extrapolated from their respective calibration curves by using the area under the curves. The results and its statistical data are over the study as per ICH norms, where to a pre analyzed sample solution standard solutions of drugs were added equivalent to Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate 80,100 and 120% of its drug content.

The percentage of drug recoveries of Ascorbic acid in 80,100 and 120% were 99.96, 100.6 and 99.96, the percentage of drug recoveries of Nicotinamide in 80.100 and 120% were 99.86, 100.31 and 100.59, the percentage of drug recoveries of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride in 80.100 and 120% were 99.83, 100.09 and 99.80, the percentage of drug recoveries of Folic Acid 80.100 and 120% were 100.30, 100.80 and 100.40, the percentage of drug recoveries of Riboflavin 80.100 and 120% were 99.75, 99.89 and 100.35 and the percentage of drug recoveries of Thiamine nitrate 80.100 and 120% were 99.66, 99.18 and 99.45 respectively. As all the statistical results were within the range of acceptance the % RSD < 2.0 and S.D. < 1.0, hence the method was accurate for simultaneous quantitative estimation of all the six drugs Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate. The statistical data and its results are reported in Table IV and V respectively. Intermediate precision study was carried out by doing intra-day and inter-day precision study. Here, six replicates of sample solutions were prepared from the stock solution. For intra- day precision study, concentrations of all the six drugs were calculated for six times on the same day at an interval of 1 hour. The statistical data are reported in Table VI. In inter-day study the concentration of drug contents were calculated on three different days (1st, 2nd and 3rd day). The statistical data are reported in Table V. The results for LOD and LOQ values were calculated to find the detection limit and quantization limit by injecting progressively low concentration of the standard solutions with the optimized

chromatographic conditions. The results are reported in Table VI. For linearity study from the standard stock solutions of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate different dilutions were prepared for each drug. Then, 20 μ L of these solutions were injected into the LC system with the help of Hamilton syringe. Then the chromatograms were recorded at 280 nm. From the chromatogram it was clear that retention time of Ascorbic acid 2.7 min, Nicotinamide 4.7 min, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride 5.6 min, Folic Acid 6.3 min, Riboflavin 8.3 min and Thiamine nitrate 14 min. Calibration curve was plotted between the areas against their respective concentrations. From the calibration curve, it was clear that Ascorbic acid has linearity range between 375-1125 μ g/mL, Nicotinamide has linearity range between 250-750 μ g/mL, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride has linearity range between 15- 45 μ g/mL, Folic Acid has linearity range between 5- 15 μ g/mL, Riboflavin has linearity range between 50-150 μ g/mL, Thiamine nitrate has linearity range between 50-150 μ g/mL, The system suitability was checked by injecting the standard solution and the results found within the range. The retention times obtained for Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate were 2.7 min, 4.5 min, 5.6 min, 6.3 min, 8.3 min and 14.0 min respectively. The resolution each drug is more than 2 for Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate. The results of capacity factor, tailing factor, theoretical plate number are reported in Table VII.

Fig. VII: Chromatograph of sample solution

Table I: Area of marketed formulation at respective retention time

S. No	Ascorbic acid at R_t 2.7 min	Nicotinamide at R_t 4.5 min	Pyridoxine Hydrochloride at R_t 5.6 min	Folic Acid at R_t 5.6 min	Riboflavin at R_t 8.3 min	Thiamine nitrate At R_t 14.0 min
1	2145231	2077839	615932	934988	6353590	1742316
2	2142142	2069888	615873	933564	6353113	1721431
3	2143575	2089090	619876	934591	6354493	1765321
4	2147551	2087320	619430	933998	6348455	1721531
5	2145252	2091257	619565	943650	6214895	1713144
6	2146179	2092144	622985	939973	6432283	1723224

Table II: Result of analysis of marketed formulation

Expected conc µg/mL						Concentration found µg/mL						% Found					
A	N	P	F	RF	T	A	N	P	F	R	T	A	N	P	F	R	T
A	A	D	A		N	A	A	D	A	F	N	A	A	D	A	F	N
75	50	30	10	10	10	74.	49	29	9.	99	99	99.	99.	10	99	99	99
0	0			0	0	91	9.	.9	99	.6	.7	34	84	0.	.9	.6	.7
							21	8		5	5			36		5	5
75	50	30	10	10	10	73.	49	30	10	98	99	98.	99.	10	10	98	99
0	0			0	0	99	8.	.1	.1	.9	.1	65	70	0.	1.	.9	.1
							52	1	0	8	0			11	0	8	0
75	50	30	10	10	10	75.	49	29	9.	99	99	10	99.	99	98	99	99
0	0			0	0	01	7.	.8	85	.2	.3	0.0	59	.5	.5	.2	.3
							99	5		3	2	1				3	2
75	50	30	10	10	10	75.	50	29	9.	99	99	10	10	98	98	99	99
0	0			0	0	11	0.	.5	82	.4	.8	0.1	0.2	.4	.2	.4	.8
							22	4		5	7	4	2	6		5	7
75	50	30	10	10	10	74.	49	29	9.	99	99	99.	99.	99	99	99	99
0	0			0	0	86	9.	.7	91	.1	.4	81	84	.1	.1	.1	.4
							23	5		2	8			6		2	8
75	50	30	10	10	10	74.	49	30	10	98	10	98.	99.	10	10	98	10
0	0			0	0	21	9.	.1	.1	.2	0.	94	97	0.	1.	.2	0.
							85	5		7	01			5	0	7	01

Table III: Result from assay of capsule formulation

Drugs	LabelClaim (mg)	Amount found in mg	Percentage purity	% RSD
Ascorbic acid	75	74.91	99.88	0.88
Nicotinamide	50	50.78	101.55	0.12
Pyridoxine HCl	3	3.00	99.84	0.45
Folic acid	1	1.02	101.87	0.80
Riboflavin	10	9.97	99.70	0.91
Thiamine Nitrate	10	10.07	100.69	1.02

Table IV: Result of recovery studies

sn o	Amount added (mg)						%	Amount found (mg) recovery											%	
	AA	N A	P D	F A	RF	T N		AA	N A	PD	F A	RF	TN	AA	N A	PD	FA	RF		T N
1	60.6	39.	2.	7.	8.0	7.9	80	60.	40	2.4	8.	7.9	7.9	99.8	10	99.	10	99.	99	
	1	98	40	98	2	8		60	.0	0	00	7	7	5	0.	83	0.3	57	.6	
								6							14		0		3	
2	60.3	40.	2.	7.	7.9	7.9	10	60.	40	2.3	7.	8.0	8.0	100.	10	99.	10	99.	10	
	3	03	40	95	9	6		21	.0	9	97	0	1	18	0.	75	0.3	96	0.	
								1							03				10	
3	60.8	40.	2.	7.	8.0	8.0	10	60.	39	2.3	7.	7.9	7.9	99.8	99	99.	10	99.	99	
	8	4	40	92	1	1		59	.7	9	93	8	4	7	.4	73	0.2	73	.5	
								6							0				2	
1	74.8	50.	3.	9.	10.	10.	10	74.	49	3.0	10	10.	9.9	100.	99	10	10	10	99	
	1	06	0	93	04	04		92	.8	1	.0	03	3	92	.6	0.3	0.7	0.2	.2	
								3							6	1		9	8	
2	75.2	49.	3.	9.	10.	9.9	10	75.	50	3.0	10	9.9	9.9	100.	10	99.	10	99.	99	
	3	97	0	50	05	8		19	.4	0	.1	6	2	09	0.	95	0.6	58	.1	
								8							95				8	
3	75.6	49.	3.	9.	10.	10.	10	75.	50	3.5	10	9.9	9.9	100.	10	10	10	99.	99	
	5	99	60	89	02	03		17	.1	8	.0	8	1	95	0.	0.0	1.1	80	.0	
								6							32	0			8	
1	90.5	59.	3.	12	11.	12.	12	90.	60	3.5	12	11.	11.	100.	10	99.	10	99.	99	
	4	99	60	.1	97	03		3.	.1	8	.1	99	98	46	0.	36	0.2	92	.5	
				1				4			3				68				3	
2	90.1	59.	3.	12	12.	12.	12	90.	60	3.6	12	12.	11.	100.	10	10	10	10	99	
	4	94	60	.1	04	01		29	.3	1	.1	06	94	21	0.	0.4	0.6	0.5	.2	
				2				8			9				63	1		2	1	
3	90.9	60.	3.	12	11.	11.	12	90.	60	3.5	12	12.	11.	99.2	10	99.	10	10	99	

	4	11	60	.1	99	99		77	.2	9	.1	07	95	0	0.	64	0.5	0.6	.6
				1					8		6				46			0	2

Table V: statistical report of recovery studies

Drug	Concentration rage	Mean	%RSD
Ascorbic acid	80%	99.96	0.2
	100%	100.6	0.5
	120%	99.96	0.7
Nicotinamide	80%	99.86	0.4
	100%	100.31	0.6
	120%	100.59	0.1
Pyridoxine HCl	80%	99.83	0.3
	100%	100.09	0.2
	120%	99.80	0.5
Folic acid	80%	100.30	0.1
	100%	100.80	0.3
	120%	100.40	0.2
Riboflavin	80%	99.75	0.2
	100%	99.89	0.4
	120%	100.35	0.4
Thiamine Nitrate	80%	99.66	0.4
	100%	99.18	0.1
	120%	99.45	0.2

Table VI: Intraday and Inter day Precision

Intraday Precision							Inter day Precision						
% Label claim							% Label claim						
	AA	NA	PD	FA	RF	T N		A A	N A	PD	FA	RF	TN
After 1hr	100. 8	99.6	100 .0	99.7	99.3		First day	99. 8	99. 5	99. 8	99. 3	99. 2	99.4
After 2hr	100. 3	99.5	100 .7	100. 5	100. 1								
After 3hr	99.5	99.2	99. 7	99.4	99.0		Second day	99. 5	99. 8	99. 5	99. 7	99. 6	99.3
After 4hr	100. 4	100.7	99. 6	100. 3	100. 4								
After 5hr	99.3	99..9	99. 0	99.4	99.6		Third day	99. 2	99. 1	99 6	99. 6	99. 4	99.6
After 6hr	100. 8	100	99. 2	100. 3	99.6								
Mean	100. 15	100.19	99. 92	100. 83	99.9 0		Mean	99. 5	99. 4	99. 6	99. 5	99. 4	99.4
SD	0.57	0.65	0.5 8	0.55	0.5		SD	0.2 3	0.5 3	0.4 1	0.4 5	0.2 1	0.21
%RSD	0.6	.06	0.6	0.6	0.5		%RSD	0.4	0.6 5	0.2 5	0.4	0.3 4	0.71

Table VII: results for system suitability

property	AA	NA	PD	FA	RF	TN
R ^t	2.7	4.5	5.6	6.3	8.3	14.0
T _f	0.12	1.18	1.18	0.64	0.98	1.02
N	8963	4859	4800	8544	9329	6400
R _s	10.6					

RESULTS

From optimized chromatographic conditions the developed method, it was found that retention time of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and thiamine nitrate were 2.7 min, 4.5 min, 5.6 min, 6.3 min, 8.3 min and 14.0 min (Fig.1), respectively, with a resolution of each peaks was found more than 2 min between the all peaks. The mean percentage of drug content in capsule dosage form (FOURTS B) was performed by performing replicate study. From the result, total content of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and Thiamine nitrate were found to be 99.88%, 101.55%, 99.84%, 101.87%, 99.70% and 100.69% with a standard deviation of 0.612, 0.937, 0.123, 0.541, 1.020 and 0.365, respectively. The percentage of drug recoveries for Ascorbic acid in 80,100 and 120% were 99.96, 100.60 and 99.96, for Nicotinamide were 99.86, 100.31 and 100.59, for Pyridoxine Hydrochloride in 80,100 and 120% were 99.83, 100.09 and 99.80, for Folic Acid in 80,100 and 120% were 100.30, 100.80 and 100.40, Riboflavin in 80,100 and 120% were 99.75, 99.89 and 100.35 and for Thiamine nitrate were 99.66, 99.18 and 99.45, respectively. In intra-day study, the sample solutions were analyzed on the same day at an interval of 1 h for 6 h and the total drug content in it measured. From the results it was observed that Ascorbic acid drug content in (mg) was 75.62, 75.01, 75.51, 0.38, 100.50%, Nicotinamide drug content in mg was 50.24, 50.40, 50.38, 0.26, 100.68%, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride drug content in mg was 2.99, 3.02, 3.02, 0.32, 100.3, Folic acid drug content in mg was 1.00, 1.00, 1.01, 0.11, 100.33, Riboflavin drug content in mg was 10.03, 10.08, 9.97, 0.32, 102.6% and Thiamine nitrate was 10.06, 10.05, 10.01 0.12, 100.4% and six hour, respectively. In inter-day study the sample solutions were analyzed on 1st, 2nd and 3rd day. From the results it was found that Ascorbic acid drug content (mg) was found to 74.58, 74.77, 75.02, 0.55, 99.76%, Nicotinamide drug content (mg) was found to 49.90, 50.67, 50.04, 0.65, 100.36%, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride drug content (mg) was found 3.01, 2.98, 3.01, 0.32, 100.0%, Folic acid drug content (mg) was found to 0.99, 1.00, 1.00, 0.21, 99.61%, Riboflavin drug content (mg) was found 10.03, 10.08, 9.97, 0.32, 102.6% and Thiamine nitrate drug content (mg) was found 10.06, 10.05, 10.01 0.12, 100.4% respectively. Both intra and inter day accuracy were within acceptability criteria. For precision study the % COV was within acceptability criteria, < 2, indicating the method was precise for quantitative estimation of all the six drugs. The developed methods for simultaneous estimation of Ascorbic acid, Nicotinamide, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, Folic Acid, Riboflavin and thiamine nitrate in capsule dosage form using reverse phase results of validation study were within the acceptance range. This reveals that the development methods were reverse phase HPLC were statistically significant as the statistical results of validation study were within the acceptance range Table VIII. This reveals that the development methods were within the acceptance range. Also, the developed method was simple, accurate, precise, economic, selective and specific method for simultaneous estimation of all the six drugs of water soluble vitamins from commercially available dosage form.

Table VIII: Validation parameters of optimized method

S. No	Parameter	Ascorbic acid	Nicotiamide	Pyridoxine HCl	Folic acid	Riboflavin	Thiamine nitrate	
1	Linearity	Correlation coefficient (r²)						r²= 1
		0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999	
2	Range	%RSD For 50%						%RSD NMT 2.0%
		0.30	0.25	0.71	0.65	0.52	0.18	
		%RSD For 150%						
		0.29	0.30	0.59	0.51	0.29	0.80	
3	Accuracy	% Recovery						90.0 % to 110.0 %
		100.17	100.25	99.90	100.5	99.99	99.43	
4	Precision	%RSD						%RSD NMT 2.0%
	System Precision	0.1	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.9	
	Method Precision	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4	
	Intermediate Precision	0.8	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6	
	Comparison between Method and Intermediate Precision	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	
5	Robustness	No deliberate change in retention time with Slight change in wavelength[278nm and 282 nm] and column oven temperature [25°C and 35°C]						%RSD NMT 2.0%
6	Specificity	No interference observed in both Blank Solution and Placebo solution						No interference observed
7	Filter integrity	No significant interference while using different 0.45μ membrane filters						% deviation ± 2

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors would like to thanks to the Principal and Management of JKKMMRF's Annai JKK SampooraniAmmal College of Pharmacy, Komarapalayam; and The Madras Pharmaceuticals, Chennai, for providing laboratory facilities to carry out this work.

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